

USE OF PEA IN THE DIET THERAPY OF CHRONIC LIVER DISEASES

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Acute viral hepatitis in most cases of chronic liver disease (B, C, D), alcohol, toxic factors, certain drugs and other conditions. According to the World Health Organization, every year 50 million people become infected with hepatitis B, 100-200 million with hepatitis C, and 350 million patients are carriers of the hepatitis C virus.

In the process of evolution, the digestive system has the ability to assimilate local products, the chemical composition of local products (Central Asian cereals, vegetables, herbs, etc.) is higher than that of imported products, various drugs are used in large quantities. In the treatment of diseases, including chronic liver diseases, they are used without paying attention to diet therapy (diet therapy).

Purpose of the study. The use of "Parhez Mohora", prepared according to a new technology, in the diet therapy of patients with chronic hepatitis and the study of their clinical effectiveness.

Material and research methods. 70 patients with chronic liver diseases were under observation. The patients were divided into two groups: Patients of the 1st group received traditional diet therapy, and Patients of the 2nd group received diet therapy using the new drug Parhez Mohora. A total of 44 Patients were examined to evaluate traditional diet therapy in Patients of the 1st group. The use of "Parhez Mohora" in the 2nd group of patients was studied in a total of 26 patients.

For 10 days, patients in the control group received dietary amanita as the 1st meal at lunch and were treated with traditional medicine (according to the norms approved by doctors). The study used clinical, laboratory, nutritional and statistical methods.

Results and discussion. In order to determine the effectiveness of diet therapy in patients, clinical signs of chronic liver diseases were monitored, biochemical blood tests were checked: ALT, AST, total bilirubin, total protein, and general blood counts. The

results obtained upon admission of the patient to the hospital were compared with the results obtained after diet therapy.

According to the results of biochemical analysis of those examined to assess the effectiveness of traditional diet therapy for chronic liver diseases, ALT decreased by 9.0%, AST decreased by 8.8%, total bilirubin decreased by 9.9%, and total protein increased by 4.8%. In the general blood test, we see that hemoglobin increased by 6.0%, the number of erythrocytes increased by 4.8%, the number of leukocytes decreased by 3.4%, the NER decreased by 10.8%.

According to the results of biochemical analyzes with diet therapy with Parhez Mohora in chronic liver diseases, ALT decreased by 16.4%, AST decreased by 8.8%, total bilirubin decreased by 9.7%, and total protein increased by 8.6%. In the general blood test, we see that hemoglobin increased by 7.5%, the number of erythrocytes increased by 5.9%, the number of leukocytes decreased by 2.0%, the NER decreased by 10.7%. In the study of traditional diet therapy for chronic liver diseases, positive changes in clinical and laboratory parameters were observed to a certain extent.

Conclusion. Compared to traditional diet therapy, the nutritional value of diet therapy with the addition of the new "Parhez Mohory" was increased from vegetable proteins to total protein, total fat to vegetable oil, carbohydrates to starch, monosaccharides-disaccharides, vitamins to E, C, PP, vitamins of group B, and somewhat reduced protein deficiency, contributed to the normal growth and development of liver tissue, increased vascular elasticity, prevented the development of fatty infiltration of the liver, activated intestinal motility, eliminated constipation, and reduced putrefactive processes in large intestines.

While following a diet for hepatitis B, C, D, it is important not to overeat, eat fractionally 4-5 times a day approximately every 3 hours. Drink 1.5-2 liters of pure water per day. It will also have a positive effect on the functioning of the liver. Due to the slow recovery of liver function after acute viral hepatitis, the patient must adhere to a diet for 4-6 months.

List of used literature:

1. Abdukadirova, L. K., Jalolov, N. N., Nozimjonova, M. N., & Narzullayeva, U. S. (2022). EVALUATION OF PRACTICAL NUTRITION OF PATIENTS WITH CHRONIC HEPATITIS.

2. Jalolov, N. N., & Imamova, A. O. (2023). THE ROLE OF NUTRITION IN THE MANAGEMENT OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS. European International Journal of Multidisciplinary Research and Management Studies, 3(02), 28-34.
3. Zokirkhodjayev, S. Y., Jalolov, N. N., Ibragimova, M. M., & Makhmudova, I. A. (2019). THE USE OF LOCAL LEGUMES IN THE DIET THERAPY OF CHRONIC HEPATITIS. Toshkent tibbiyot akademiyasi axborotnomasi, (1), 64-68.
4. ПАТТАХОВА, М., & МУТАЛОВ, С. (2022). Жигарнинг дори-дармонлар таъсирида зарарланиши (Doctoral dissertation, Ўзбекистан, Ташкент).
5. Salomova, F. I., Rakhimov, B. B., Jalolov, N. N., Sultonov, E. Y., & Oblakulov, A. G. (2023). ATMOSPHERIC AIR OF THE CITY OF NAVOI: QUALITY ASSESSMENT. British Journal of Global Ecology and Sustainable Development, 15, 121-125.
6. Жалолов, Н., Зокирходжаев, Ш. Я., & Саломова, Ф. И. (2022, May). Сурункали гепатит билан касалланган беморларнинг ҳақиқий овқатланишини баҳолаш. «Тиббиётдаги замонавий илмий тадқиқотлар: долзарб муаммолар, ютуқлар ва инновациялар»//мавзусидаги халқаро илмий-амалий конференция.
7. Mirsagatova, M. R., & Obloqulov, A. G. (2023). DISEASES OF THE GASTROINTESTINAL TRACT AGAINST THE BACKGROUND OF FOOD ALLERGIES IN CHILDREN OF EARLY AND PRESCHOOL AGE. INTERNATIONAL CONFERENCE ON HIGHER EDUCATION TEACHING.
8. Jalolov, N. (2017). Жигар касалликларида Ибн Сино қарашлари ва замонавий тиббиётда беморлар ҳаққоний овқатланишини касаллик ривожланишидаги ўрни.
9. Закирходжаев, Ш. Я., Жалолов, Н. Н., Абдукадилова, Л. К., & Мирсагатова, М. Р. (2023). ЗНАЧЕНИЕ ПИТАНИЯ ПРИ ХРОНИЧЕСКИХ ГЕПАТИАХ.
10. Jalolov, N., & Solihov, M. (2017). Сурункали жигар касалликларида ҳаққоний овқатланиш ҳолатини ўрганиш.
11. Зокирхўжаев, Ш. Я., Рустамова, М. Т., Паттахова, М. Х., Жалолов, Н. Н., & Муталов, С. Б. (2023). Сурункали жигар касалликларида соғлом овқатланишнинг аҳамияти.

12. Зокирхужаев, Ш. Я., Рустамова, М. Т., Паттахова, М. Х., Нарзиев, Н. М., Жалолов, Н. Н., & Муталов, С. Б. (2023). Коронавирус инфекцияси ва жигар зарарланиши.

13. Зокирходжаев, Ш. Я., Жалолов, Н. Н., Ибрагимова, М. М., & Махмудова, И. А. (2019). Сурункали гепатитлар парҳезтерапиясида маҳаллий дуккакли маҳсулотларни қўллаш.

14. Jalolov, N., & Parpiboeva, D. A. (2017). Лечебное питание при хронических заболеваниях печени.